

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Deliverable D5.4 - Connect the dots: translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building

WP5 – Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

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HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

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Document History

Deliverable Title	Connect the dots: translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building
Brief Description	This deliverable compile and translates the capacity-building resources developed within Adaptation AGORA into a harmonised set of multilingual one-pagers. It enhances accessibility, cross-regional learning, and knowledge exchange by disseminating these materials through the Digital Handbook “Voices of Climate Adaptation”, the AGORA Community Hub, and external open-access platforms.
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Sept 2025	V0	Lucía Moreno, Judith Bielsa	Collecting information. Writing the first draft
Sept 2025	V1	Alfredo Reder, Lucía Moreno, Judith Bielsa	Reviewing the draft and completing the updates.
Oct 2025	V2	Nefertari Nachtigall, François Jost, Lucía Moreno, Judith Bielsa	Reviewing the draft and completing the updates.
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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Introduction	4
2.1 Project background and the aim of the task.....	4
2.2 Link to Tasks 5.1–5.3 and other capacity building resources from the project.....	5
2.3 Implementation of the task	5
3. Set of capacity building resources: synthesis & multilingual adaptation	6
3.1 One-pager structure.....	6
3.1.1 One-pager template.....	7
3.2 Capacity building resources mapping	7
3.3 Multilingual adaptation.....	9
4. Dissemination.....	10
5. References.....	11
6. Annexes.....	12
Annex 1. Zenodo: Matrix, Mapping task 5.4 Connect the dots, translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building	12
Annex 2. Zenodo: Capacity building resources	13
Annex 3. Digital Handbook “Voices of Climate Adaptation”	14
Annex 4. AGORA Community Hub	14
Annex 5. CitizenScience.eu	15
Annex 6: WeADAPT	15

1. Executive Summary

The Deliverable D5.4 “Connect the dots: translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building” brings together the capacity-building resources (CBRs) developed across the Adaptation AGORA project, with a particular focus on those produced within Work Package 5. It aims to consolidate, translate, and disseminate these resources in a harmonised, user-friendly format that facilitates their accessibility, understanding, and uptake by a wide range of stakeholders.

The resulting set of one-pagers represents a coherent collection of materials designed to support learning and knowledge transfer on climate adaptation. Each one-pager summarises a specific capacity-building resource, providing key information on its objectives, target audience, challenges addressed, and practical contributions. The one-pager format was chosen for its clarity, comparability, and usability. All materials have been translated into the seven consortium languages — Italian, Spanish, Swedish, German, Greek, French and Estonian — using inclusive and easy-to-understand language to ensure that the content is accessible to diverse audiences across partner regions.

To maximise visibility and long-term impact, the one-pagers have been disseminated through several interconnected platforms. The complete set has been published on Zenodo under a unified DOI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183255>), where each file can also be accessed individually. From Zenodo, the collection feeds into other platforms, including the Digital Handbook “Voices of Climate Adaptation”, the AGORA Community Hub, and external knowledge-sharing environments such as EU-Citizen.Science and weADAPT.

In doing so, Deliverable D5.4 not only consolidates the project’s capacity-building outcomes but also contributes to the broader mission of fostering inclusive, evidence-based, and participatory approaches to climate resilience across Europe.

2. Introduction

2.1 Project background and the aim of the task

This report is part of the EU-funded Horizon Europe project Adaptation AGORA – A Gathering place to co-design and co-create Adaptation. The project supports communities and regions engaged in the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change by fostering inclusive approaches that enable citizens and stakeholders to actively contribute to the design and implementation of adaptation measures.

The aim of the report is to bring together the capacity-building resources developed in the Adaptation AGORA journey and make them accessible in a multi-language format. This process improves accessibility, promotes cross-regional learning, and strengthens the replicability of good practices across regions and communities. The resources have been grouped and introduced through a set of one-pagers.

The translated materials provide stakeholders with practical guidance to enhance their ability to design, implement and replicate adaptation initiatives. These outputs will also contribute to the Digital Handbook “Voices of Climate Adaptation” (Task 6.2), the Digital Agora (now AGORA Community Hub) (Task 3.3) and other online platforms, thereby maximising their reach and impact.

More specifically, the task aimed to:

- Compile and synthesise resources from WP5.
- Translate materials into Consortium languages.
- Promote cross-regional knowledge exchange and replication.
- Provide practical guidance to strengthen capacity building.
- Support dissemination through the Digital Handbook, the Agora Community Hub and external platforms, Zenodo, citizenscience.eu, climate ADAPT, weADAPT.

2.2 Link to Tasks 5.1–5.3 and other capacity building resources from the project

Task 5.4 builds upon the capacity-building resources generated in Tasks 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3 by compiling and synthesising the outputs produced. While the primary focus of this task is on the materials created within the scope of WP5, additional capacity-building resources developed across other work packages have also been incorporated. Although the task was originally confined to the inclusion of capacity-building resources from WP5, we broadened the scope to include relevant resources from other work packages as well, thereby ensuring their representation and enhancing the overall value of the compilation. This broader integration not only reinforces the connection between Task 5.4 and the wider objectives of the Adaptation AGORA project but also provides a more comprehensive approach that captures insights and practices across multiple dimensions of the project.

In line with the project’s overall objective, Task 5.4 follows the definition of capacity-building resources (CBRs) defined in Deliverable 5.1. (Report on co-production of capacity building resources): *CBRs are tools and materials that help individuals and organisations build the necessary skills, knowledge, and resources for effective climate adaptation. Used primarily in workshops, training, and community engagement, these resources enhance participants’ knowledge and increase resilience by addressing power dynamics and vulnerabilities (Blake et al., 2021).* In this sense, the compilation carried out in Task 5.4 has integrated CBRs originating from other work packages, such as WP2 and WP3.

2.3 Implementation of the task

The planning and implementation of the task have been broken down into three different activities, taking place in 2025 ([Table 1](#)):

- **Activity A5.4.1:** Generate a one-pager for every CBR produced in 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3.

- **Activity A5.4.2:** Translate the one-pagers to the different languages used within the Consortium. The translations will prioritise easy-to-understand and inclusive language, adding specific clarifications when necessary.
- **Activity A5.4.3:** Distribution of the one-pagers across various platforms.

Table 1. Implementation plan

Task	D	2025											
		J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O		
T5.4 (IBE)													
A5.4.1													
A5.4.2													
A5.4.3													

3. Set of capacity building resources: synthesis & multilingual adaptation

3.1 One-pager structure

The structure of the one-pager, organised into five key sections, ensures that each CBR is readily identifiable, accessible, and meaningful to a wide range of users within and beyond the project.

1. **Link to the material.** This section guarantees traceability and direct access to the original resource.
2. **Category and target audience.** The thematic classification and identification of the intended audience help direct the CBR towards those actors who can benefit most.
3. **Summary and basic information.** Providing a concise introduction together with essential metadata (such as estimated time of use, objectives, type of resource, and language) improves accessibility and initial comprehension.
4. **Challenges and issues addressed.** By outlining the key challenges the resource responds to, this section situates it within the context of real adaptation needs.
5. **Contributions and added value of the resource.** Describing what the CBR offers — whether practical guidance, methodologies, examples, or expert insights — is essential for potential users to anticipate its usefulness and benefits. This section transforms the CBR into a tangible tool for action, promoting knowledge transfer and supporting replicability across different regional contexts.

Taken together, these five elements ensure that the CBRs are not perceived as isolated outputs but rather as strategic instruments within the **Adaptation AGORA** capacity-building framework, thereby maximising their reach, impact, and sustainability.

3.1.1 One-pager template

Resource title

Under the capacity building activities, Adaptation AGORA has been developing different materials. They range from multimedia materials, like videos, recordings of webinars/conferences, to sets of slides, as well as content for the development of the two Academies. Adaptation AGORA is not responsible for the use of the materials (CC BY).

1. Link to the material

2. Potential key entries to search material.
 Category:
 Target:

3. Brief Introduction/Summary
 Estimated time:
 Objective:
 Type of resource: ppt, excel, graph
 Language:

4. Key Challenges/ issues addressed

5. What the Resource Offers
 Practical Guidance: Describe the tools or frameworks included (e.g., adaptation measures, mitigation pathways, capacity building methodologies, examples from other projects, insights from experts).
 Localized Insights: Explain how the resource tailors its recommendations to regional challenges. - if available

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adaptationagora.eu

1

3.2 Capacity building resources mapping

As part of Task 5.4, a matrix under the DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432564> (see [Annex 1](#)) was developed to systematically map the CBRs produced across the project ([Table 1](#)). This tool provided a structured and transparent overview of the different resources by capturing key information such as their type, objectives, target groups, challenges addressed, and practical outputs. In doing so, it facilitated their synthesis into accessible formats, such as the one-pagers, thereby enhancing clarity, comparability, and usability for stakeholders across regions and sectors.

In addition to this structured mapping exercise, a participatory activity was conducted during the General Assembly in Berlin. In this session, project partners were invited to share the CBRs embedded in their respective work packages. These contributions were then captured under the “miscellanea” category of the matrix and subsequently integrated into the compilation of one-pagers. This collaborative approach complemented the systematic mapping by uncovering additional resources that might not have been immediately visible, thus ensuring a more comprehensive and representative collection. By combining structured analysis with participatory input, Task 5.4 achieved a robust and inclusive mapping of CBRs, which strengthens the overall value, visibility, and replicability of the project’s outputs.

Table 2. Summary of capacity-building materials

Capacity Building Material	Original language	Objective
What is adaptation to climate change?	English	Inform the general public on adaptation, defining adaptation & importance of citizen engagement
What is climate misinformation?	English	Explain climate misinformation & inform on misinformation resources from John Cook
Methodologies to address climate misinformation	English	Sharing insights into the most effective techniques for combating misinformation, while also promoting media and climate literacy.
Climate change: challenges and solutions	English	Explain to the general public, who is interested, the scientific bases of climate change
Adaptation AGORA project, activities in the Roman pilot	English	Empower university students & the general public by addressing climate adaptation issues in the region via a multi-dimensional approach & showcasing strategies to combat disinformation
Adaptation AGORA digital tools	English	Overview of Digital Tools created by Adaptation Agora
Adaptation AGORA academy on climate data	English	Overview of the Academy on Climate Data and its use
Build up twinning Agoras: online cross-regional peer-to-peer activities	English, Italian	The peer-to-peer learning events aimed at creating a space for connecting and exchanging challenges, opportunities and

		tools for citizens' engagement in climate adaptation. Type of resource: Videos
Materials to enhance media literacy and combat climate change disinformation	English	Enhance media literacy skills; Provide tools to combat disinformation; Promote climate literacy
Glossary SEI OX	English	Provide a common reference of terms, concepts, and sources relevant to climate change adaptation, supporting consistency across project outputs.
Focus Group summaries from Pilot Regions	English	Synthesise the results of focus groups conducted in pilot regions (Spain, Italy, Sweden, and Germany) as part of co-creation and co-evaluation processes for soft adaptation solutions. The sessions engaged diverse demographic groups—including youth, workers, multicultural communities, the elderly, and vulnerable populations—to explore climate adaptation needs, solutions, and engagement methodologies.
Heat and heat protection measures in the health system (Original: Hitzeschutzmaßnahmen für Pflegefachkräfte)	German	Raise awareness among nursing and medical staff about the risks related to heat and the possibilities for introducing heat protection measures.
Climate adaptation and the components of vulnerability (Original: Klimaanpassung und Klimavulnerabilität)	German	Equip participants with basic knowledge about climate adaptation. Used during the info-event offered right before the Inception Workshop (in Dresden).

3.3 Multilingual adaptation

Translating the one-pagers into the languages of the Consortium is a strategic step to ensure that the knowledge and practices developed within the project are genuinely inclusive and actionable. By making the CBRs available in multiple languages, the project fosters cross-regional learning, enabling stakeholders from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds to engage meaningfully with the materials. This enhances the replicability of good practices across all partner regions, as stakeholders can internalise, adapt, and apply the guidance within their specific contexts. Moreover,

presenting CBRs in local languages supports a multidimensional process of change, as it reduces barriers to participation and empowers a wider range of actors to contribute to climate resilience.

The translations will prioritise easy-to-understand and inclusive language, adding specific clarifications when necessary. This ensures that the CBRs are not only technically accurate but also approachable, thereby maximising their practical value. In doing so, the translated materials become not only a tool for knowledge transfer but also a catalyst for capacity building, strengthening stakeholders' ability to design, implement, and replicate adaptation activities across different scales.

The languages of the Consortium are English, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Spanish and Swedish.

4. Dissemination

Disseminating the one-pagers beyond the immediate project channels constitutes a deliberate strategy that maximises their visibility, usability, and long-term impact. The resources already feed into the Digital Handbook "Voices of Climate Adaptation" (Task 6.2) (see [Annex 3](#)) and the AGORA Community Hub (Task 3.3) (see [Annex 4](#)), while their circulation through additional online platforms such as Zenodo (see [Annex 2](#)), CitizenScience.eu (see [Annex 5](#)) and weADAPT (see [Annex 6](#)), extends their reach to a broader community of practitioners, researchers, and policymakers engaged in climate adaptation. This wider diffusion generates opportunities for cross-fertilisation of knowledge, as the resources are accessed, discussed, and adapted by stakeholders beyond the project's direct sphere.

By ensuring that the one-pagers are present on well-established and widely used platforms, the project strengthens their replicability and practical application across different regions and sectors. This strategy enhances the visibility of the outputs and positions them as valuable contributions within existing European and global knowledge ecosystems.

Zenodo acts as the principal repository that subsequently feeds into other platforms (see [Annex 2](#)), DOI number <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183255>. By adopting this strategy, the project leverages Zenodo's role as a recognised and citable open-access repository, while simultaneously ensuring that the resources are disseminated through interconnected platforms. This approach strengthens both the durability and the interoperability of the outputs.

The choice of the naming code on Zenodo was designed to balance coherence and accessibility. The thirteen files have been uploaded under a single publication that aggregates them as a unified collection, while still allowing each one-pager to be accessed individually. Each file is titled after the specific CBR it contains, thereby facilitating targeted consultation by users seeking a particular output. Furthermore, each one-pager includes the translated version of the resource in the seven

consortium languages, with annexes providing the original material when the CBR was internal to the project. This structure ensures consistency across the collection while maximising its usability for diverse audiences. The set of one-pagers can be cited as follows: Bielsa, J., & Moreno, L. (2025)—capacity building resources from the Adaptation AGORA project, set of one-pagers.

A summary article has been published on the [AGORA Community Hub](#) platform to further disseminate the one-pagers (see [Annex 4](#)). By making them available through the AGORA Community Hub, their visibility is increased beyond the immediate project channels, thereby supporting broader knowledge exchange and uptake across diverse adaptation contexts. In the Digital Handbook “Voices of Climate Adaptation” a reference to the CBRs developed under WP5 was included in the section Public Awareness (see [Annex 3](#)). The website is an interactive, multimedia resource that consolidates all the knowledge generated by the project into a comprehensive, accessible and exploitable format. The website is specifically structured to ensure the transferability and scale-up of Adaptation AGORA's results, providing a tangible legacy to the project and supporting the longevity and impact of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change well beyond the project's conclusion. The reference to the CBRs was included in the Public Awareness theme of the website to emphasise the importance of capacity building as an effective tool to engage and empower citizens and help them play a more active role in decision-making processes.

In addition to reaching a broader audience, the set of Capacity Building Resources (CBRs) has been uploaded to additional knowledge-sharing platforms, such as [EU-Citizen.Science](#) (see [Annex 5](#)), and [weADAPT](#) (see [Annex 6](#)). On the EU-Citizen.Science platform, the CBRs appear as a searchable resource under the title “Capacity building resources from the Adaptation AGORA project, set of one-pagers”. This entry is directly linked to the Zenodo repository, thereby ensuring accessibility and proper citation of the materials through a recognised open-access source. The weADAPT platform has included the CBRs in the “Agora Community Network” network, summarising the CBRs and linking directly to the Zenodo resources. In contrast, on the Climate-ADAPT platform, the explanation of the CBR set is integrated within the dedicated Adaptation AGORA project page rather than as a standalone resource. This section also provides a direct link to the Zenodo collection, allowing users to access the materials easily while situating them within the broader context of the project's objectives and outputs.

5. References

Blake, M., Pottinger, L., & Ehgartner, U. (2021). Engaged Capacity building Workshops. In *Methods for Change: Impactful social science methodologies for 21st century problems*. ASPECT.

6. Annexes

Annex 1. Zenodo: Matrix, Mapping task 5.4 Connect the dots, translate insights and lessons learned on capacity building

Published October 24, 2025 | Version v1

[Figure](#) [Open](#)

Matrix. Mapping of capacity building resources

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[Show affiliations](#)

Mapping matrix of capacity building resources created within the Adaptation AGORA Project.

Files

Annex 2. Zenodo: Capacity building resources

Published September 23, 2025 | Version v1

Publication Open

Capacity building resources from the Adaptation AGORA project, set of one-pagers

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Show affiliations

Files

Annex 3. Digital Handbook “Voices of Climate Adaptation”

Voices of Climate Adaptation
Menu ⊕

FROM AWARENESS TO ACTION

COMMUNICATION AND ENGAGEMENT

DISINFORMATION BARRIER

In Adaptation AGORA, capacity building was heavily used throughout engagement activities. Building from other EU projects and from previous project activities, Adaptation AGORA compiled the best capacity building methods for successful engagement and maximized the potential of project events. For instance, storytelling was used throughout project workshops to connect with participants and to relay climate information in a more relatable and easy to understand way.

The capacity building tools, methods, and resources gathered from other projects and from Adaptation AGORA events have been compiled into [various documents and reports](#), to help future projects, organizations, and communities apply capacity building methods to build public awareness and climate action.

Moreover, **all capacity building resources produced under the project are systematised in a [set of one-pagers](#)** which can be consulted as a catalogue. Peer-learning activities are also key to build strong networks and facilitate mutual exchange.

Annex 4. AGORA Community Hub

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Annex 5. CitizenScience.eu

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Capacity building resources from the Adaptation AGORA project, set of one-pagers

[Go to Resource](#)

The purpose of the **one-pagers in Adaptation AGORA** is to **translate and synthesise the project's capacity-building resources into a brief, accessible, and multilingual format**, facilitating their **dissemination across communities and regions**, and supporting cross-regional learning, replicability of good practices, and stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation.

The one-pagers are translated in English, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Spanish and Swedish.

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Annex 6: WeADAPT

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Agora Community Network

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